

1 **Modelling evapotranspiration in a Scots pine stand under Mediterranean**
2 **mountain climate using the GLUE methodology**

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25

26 **Abstract**

27 Canopy transpiration (E_c) and soil evaporation (E_s) in a Mediterranean Scots pine stand
28 were simulated using a two-layer model, with a Jarvis-type submodel of canopy
29 stomatal conductance (G_s) and a soil resistance to evaporation expressed as a function
30 of superficial soil moisture. Sap flow and soil evaporation measurements obtained from
31 microlysimeters, together with meteorological and soil moisture data were used to
32 calibrate the model. Calibration of G_s was carried out first with data from the year 2004,
33 using the Generalized Likelihood Uncertainty Estimation (GLUE) methodology. Then,
34 data from the year 2003, which included an intense summer drought, was used to update
35 the results from the previous calibration. The discrepancy between the diurnal courses
36 of modelled and measured E_c using best-fit parameters was not related to any particular
37 situation of meteorology or soil moisture. Model performance at the daily scale was
38 better, but still showed poor results for the year 2005. Maximum modelled E_s rates were
39 0.7 mm day^{-1} with the ratio E_s/E_c being typically under 0.3 during the growing season.
40 The GLUE analysis revealed that parameters representing reference stomatal aperture
41 and sensitivity to vapour pressure deficit (D) were the most relevant, and were
42 consistent with the hydraulic theory of stomatal regulation. Parameters controlling the
43 response to soil moisture deficit only appeared sensitive in the calibration with data
44 from the year 2003. Updating the original calibration reduced predictive uncertainty and
45 constrained the value of some parameters. Nevertheless, it seems that representations of
46 variable plant and soil hydraulic resistances are required to simulate long-term E_c under
47 in seasonally-dry Mediterranean forests.

48 **Introduction**

49 Despite the increasing efforts devoted to the development of forest evapotranspiration
50 models, very little research has been carried out in montane forests under Mediterranean
51 climate. These areas differ from other temperate locations in the overall higher
52 evaporative demand and the occurrence of extremely dry periods. Therefore,
53 evapotranspiration models to be applied in such conditions need both adequate
54 representations of physiological regulation of transpiration and control of soil factors on
55 forest floor evaporation.

56 Whereas soil surface resistance is usually modelled using simple relationships with
57 topsoil water content (Camillo and Gurney, 1986; Wallace, 1995), stomatal aperture, the
58 main determinant of plant surface resistance, can be modelled solely on the basis of
59 water relations (Jarvis, 1976), or coupling transpiration and photosynthesis (Ball et al.,
60 1987). While the use of coupled models is recommended for modelling water and CO₂
61 fluxes (Hanson, 2004), for hydrological purposes, the semi-empirical Jarvis algorithm,
62 has been shown to represent adequately the underlying physiological processes of
63 stomatal regulation (Mackay et al., 2003a).

64 In soil-vegetation-atmosphere transfer models, many parameter sets will yield
65 acceptable simulations (Franks et al., 1997; Mo and Beven, 2004), leading to a
66 equifinality problem (Beven and Freer, 2001). The Generalized Likelihood Uncertainty
67 Estimation (GLUE) methodology (Beven and Binley, 1992) can be used to deal with
68 equifinality problem, investigating the parameter space, the associated predictive
69 uncertainty, and the effect of incorporating new data into the calibration procedure
70 (Beven and Freer, 2001).

71 In this study, we modelled evapotranspiration in a Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) stand
72 using a two-layer interactive model (Shuttleworth and Wallace, 1985), which allows the

73 interaction between canopy and soil fluxes (Daamen and McNaughton, 2000) and
74 usually show superior performance than single-layer models, especially under wetter
75 conditions when the contribution from the soil is highest (Fisher et al., 2005). A similar
76 model has already been tested on this species (Iritz et al., 1999), and an extensive body
77 of literature exists addressing Scots pine physiological regulation of transpiration
78 (Irvine et al., 1998; Lagergren and Lindroth, 2002; Sturm et al., 1998) However, there is
79 scarce knowledge of the performance of Scots pine evapotranspiration models under
80 seasonally-dry environments. The aims of this study were: (a) to use soil evaporation to
81 parameterise soil resistance to evaporation, (b) to use sap flow measurements to
82 parameterise a Jarvis-type canopy conductance model within the framework of the
83 GLUE methodology, (b) to assess model performance under diverse meteorological and
84 soil moisture conditions, and (c) to investigate parameter sensitivity and predictive
85 uncertainty within the GLUE framework.

86 **Material and methods**

87 *Site and stand characteristics*

88 The experimental plot is part of the Vallcebre research area (42° 12' N, 1° 49' E),
89 located in the Eastern Pyrenees (NE Spain) at an elevation of ca. 1260 m.a.s.l. The
90 oldest trees in the stand are about 60 years old, and stem density and basal area are 2165
91 trees ha⁻¹ and 44.7 m² ha⁻¹, respectively. Mean diameter at breast height (DBH) is ca. 15
92 cm and leaf area index (LAI) is 2.4 m² m⁻². The understorey is scarce, mainly scattered
93 *Buxus sempervirens* L. shrubs, and a discontinuous herb layer. Mudstone and sandstone
94 are the principal underlying lithologies, originating sandy-loam soils about 65 cm deep
95 (Rubio, personal communication). Climate is sub-Mediterranean, with an average air
96 temperature of 7.3 °C (measured at 1440 m.a.s.l.) and 924 mm of annual rainfall
97 (Gallart et al., 2002). The present landscape is a mosaic of mesophilous grassland of the

98 *Aphyllantion* type and patches of Scots pine, which colonised old agricultural terraces
99 after their abandonment (Poyatos et al., 2003).

100 *Meteorological, soil moisture and sap flow measurements*

101 Above-canopy meteorology, volumetric water content in the top 30 cm of the soil, and
102 sap flow by the heat dissipation method (Granier, 1985) were measured continuously
103 between June 2003 and August 2005, recording average values at a 15-min time step.
104 For further details of meteorological and soil moisture instrumentation see Poyatos et al.
105 (2005). Sap flow was measured in 8-11 trees using a 20 mm long heat dissipation (HD)
106 probe per tree, and then correcting for radial variation of sap flow according to
107 measured radial patterns using the Heat Field Deformation method (HFD) (Poyatos,
108 2006; Poyatos et al., 2007).

109 Below-canopy net radiation ($R_{n,s}$) and soil heat flux (G) were also measured during July
110 and August of the year 2005 to parameterise the radiative transfer within the canopy.
111 We obtained the estimates of $R_{n,s}$ by averaging the measurements from three net
112 radiometers (Q7, REBS, Seattle, WA, USA) randomly placed above the forest soil. Four
113 soil heat flux plates (HFT-3, REBS, Seattle, WA, USA) were also installed to measure
114 soil heat flux at a depth of 0.08 m, and above each plate, a set of soil thermocouples
115 (TCAV, Campbell Scientific, Shepshed, Leicestershire, UK) inserted at 0.02 and 0.06 m
116 depth, measured the average temperature of the soil layer above the plates. Calculations
117 of total soil heat flux were done following Massman (1992).

118 *Soil evaporation measurements*

119 Soil evaporation was measured in six locations randomly placed in the forest floor and
120 fitted with PVC cylinders (lysimeter cases) of 11.8 cm in diameter and 15 cm depth
121 (Daamen et al., 1993). For each measurement date, a set of 4-6 soil cores were extracted
122 by hammering a PVC tube (diameter 10.8 cm, 15 cm long) into the soil in a nearby

123 location. These lysimeters were sealed with a PVC cap and then inserted into the
124 lysimeter cases, covering the top with a plastic mesh to avoid measurement errors due to
125 litterfall. The lysimeters were weighed in the morning between 7:00-8:00 solar time,
126 and then in the evening (18:00-19:00 solar time). Soil evaporation rate was then
127 calculated from the difference in weight divided by the time between measurements.

128 *Model description and parameterisation of aerodynamic resistances*

129 The two-layer interactive model has been described elsewhere (Shuttleworth and
130 Wallace, 1985). Aerodynamic resistances were calculated assuming a logarithmic wind
131 profile, K -theory for eddy transfer (Shuttleworth and Gurney, 1990; Shuttleworth and
132 Wallace, 1985), stability corrections (Choudhury and Monteith, 1988) and characteristic
133 leaf dimensions for Scots pine (Iritz et al., 1999). Symbols and units used throughout
134 the text are listed in Table 1.

135 *Parameterisation of radiation transfer and soil heat flux*

136 Above-canopy net radiation (R_n) was partitioned between canopy (R_n^c) and soil (R_n^s)
137 according to Lambert-Beer's law. The penetration of radiation was simulated using the
138 estimated stand LAI plus a branch fraction value obtained in a nearby stand, in which
139 the parameter of an elliptical leaf angle distribution had also been estimated (Llorens
140 and Gallart, 2000). The extinction coefficient for R_n was calculated using measured
141 values of R_n and R_n^s during clear days (days 215-218, August 2005) and inverting the
142 Lambert-Beer model.

143 A preliminary analysis showed that soil heat flux (G) lagged one hour behind radiative
144 input at the forest soil. Therefore, we used 1h-lagged net radiation at the forest floor
145 ($R_{n,s,t-1}$), soil water content in the first 15 cm (θ_{0-15}) and air temperature as independent
146 variables to predict G using a multiple regression model fitted to measured data (days
147 214-221, August 2005).

148 *Parameterisation of soil surface resistance*

149 We calculated soil surface resistance to evaporation (r_s^s) as:

150
$$r_s^s = \frac{(0.622\rho/P)(e_{T_s}^* - e_r)}{E_s} - r_a^s \quad (1)$$

151 Where ρ is air density (kg m^{-3}), P is atmospheric pressure in kPa, $e_{T_s}^*$ is saturated
152 vapour pressure in soil pore space, e_r is vapour pressure at the reference height, E_s is soil
153 evaporation ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and r_a^s is soil aerodynamic resistance (s m^{-1}). We used E_s
154 measured with microlysimeters to calculate r_s^s and then relate its value to the soil
155 moisture conditions of the plot.

156 Overall, we obtained fifteen estimates of r_s^s in four measurement dates along the year
157 2005 (19 and 20th of May, 4th and 24th August). Soil surface resistance estimated for
158 each lysimeter and measuring date was related to volumetric soil moisture of the
159 lysimeter (θ_{0-15}) fitting a power relationship,

160
$$r_s^s = b_1 \left(\frac{\theta_{0-15}}{\theta_{0-15,FC}} \right)^{b_2} \quad (2)$$

161 Where $\theta_{0-15,FC}$ is the corresponding value of soil moisture at field capacity ($\theta_{0-15,FC} =$
162 $0.35 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, C.Rubio, personal communication). A linear relationship between the
163 average soil moisture of the plot in the upper 30 cm (θ_{0-30}) and θ_{0-15} was fitted in order
164 to convert continuous values of θ_{0-30} into θ_{0-15} to use them in Eq. 5 to obtain r_s^s

165 *Formulation of canopy surface resistance*

166 Canopy surface resistance (r_s^c) was defined by inverting the product of canopy stomatal
167 conductance (G_s) and stand leaf area index (LAI). LAI seasonal variation was assessed
168 using phenological observations and assuming that a fixed fraction of the maximum
169 LAI remains throughout late autumn, winter and early spring (Beadle et al., 1982).

170 Canopy stomatal conductance was calculated from stand-scaled sap flow measurements
 171 and meteorological data, using the inversion of the Penman-Monteith equation for well
 172 coupled canopies (Whitehead and Jarvis, 1981), assuming no capacitance effects and
 173 following recommendations by Ewers and Oren (2000). Then, G_s was parameterised as
 174 a function of the main meteorological variables (Jarvis, 1976). Maximum conductance
 175 $G_{s,max}$ was constrained by a series of functions which depended on R_n , air temperature
 176 (T), soil moisture deficit (SMD_{0-30}) and time of day (t):

$$177 \quad G_s = G_{s,max}(D)f_1(R_n)f_2(T)f_3(SMD_{0-30})f_4(t) \quad (4)$$

178 Soil moisture (SMD_{0-30}) deficit (ranging from 0 to 1) was calculated using the minimum
 179 and maximum values of θ_{0-30} as described in Granier and Loustau (1994). The response
 180 of G_s to D was defined by Oren et al. (1999):

$$181 \quad G_{s,max} = G_{s,ref} - m \cdot \ln D \quad (5)$$

182 The response to radiation was described by a saturating function with one parameter
 183 ($R_{n,0.5}$) representing the value of R_n at half-saturation of G_s :

$$184 \quad f_1(R_n) = \frac{R_n}{R_{n,0.5} + R_n} \quad (6)$$

185 The soil moisture function had two parameters: s , defining the threshold beyond which
 186 soil water supply limits transpiration and f_0 , meaning the fraction of transpiration that is
 187 still sustained when soil moisture deficit was complete.

$$188 \quad f_2(SMD_{0-30}) = \begin{cases} SMD_{0-30} < s \Rightarrow f_2(SMD_{0-30}) = 1 \\ s < SMD_{0-30} < 1 \Rightarrow f_2(SMD_{0-30}) = \left(\frac{f_0 - 1}{1 - s}\right)SMD_{0-30} + \left(\frac{1 - sf_0}{1 - s}\right) \end{cases}$$

$$189 \quad (7)$$

190 The resulting relationship equals 1 when $SMD_{0-30} < s$, reduces to f_0 when $SMD_{0-30} = 0$ and
 191 shows a linear decrease when $s < SMD_{0-30} < f_0$.

192 The constraint function for temperature was a quadratic function with T_{\min} , T_{\max} and T_{opt}
 193 being minimum, maximum and optimum temperatures, respectively

$$194 \quad f_3(T) = \frac{(T - T_{\min})}{(T_{\text{opt}} - T_{\min})} \cdot \frac{(T_{\max} - T)}{(T_{\max} - T_{\text{opt}})} \quad (8)$$

195 Finally as an additional dependence of G_s with time of day was observed in previous
 196 analysis, a quadratic function equivalent to that of temperature $f_4(t)$ was included to
 197 correct for this effect.

198 *Generalised Likelihood Uncertainty Estimation (GLUE)*

199 The GLUE methodology (Beven and Binley, 1992) is based on retaining, from a large
 200 sample of parameter sets, the models which are considered to be acceptable simulators
 201 of the system (or ‘behavioural’). In our application, 30,000 Monte Carlo simulations
 202 were performed using parameters randomly sampled from uniform distributions within
 203 a feasible range (Table 2). All the parameters in the G_s submodel and canopy roughness
 204 length (z_0), which affects aerodynamic resistance (Shuttleworth and Gurney, 1990),
 205 were included in the GLUE analysis (Table 2). Parameter conditioning was carried out
 206 using G_s and meteorological measurements taken during the year 2004 (Table 3). Each
 207 simulation was performed using the available meteorological data and the resulting
 208 simulated E_c was compared against experimentally measured E_c from sap flow. We
 209 computed model efficiency (E_f) (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970) for each run and used it as a
 210 likelihood measure:

$$211 \quad L(\Theta_j | Y) = E_f = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (O_i - P_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \quad (9)$$

212 $L(\Theta_j | Y)$ is the likelihood measure for the j th parameter set (Θ_j) conditioned on the
 213 observations Y . The right hand-side of the equation is model efficiency with O_i and P_i
 214 being observed and predicted values of E_c at the i th time step and \bar{O} the mean of

215 observed values. Model efficiency, whose maximum value equals 1 for a perfect fit
 216 (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970), was calculated on a daily basis and models with $E_f < 0$ were
 217 rejected.

218 Parameter sets corresponding to simulations with $E_f > 0.75$ were retained as behavioural.
 219 Then, cumulative likelihood distributions of the parameters for behavioural and non-
 220 behavioural models were compared to assess the sensitivity of each parameter. If
 221 uniform distributions were obtained (straight lines), the parameter was considered to be
 222 insensitive to the likelihood measure chosen.

223 Predictive uncertainty bounds were estimated by ranking the outputs from behavioural
 224 models according to their likelihood weights, and deriving a cumulative distribution
 225 (Franks and Beven, 1997). Likelihood weights had been previously obtained by
 226 rescaling the efficiencies of the behavioural models in order that their sum was 1. We
 227 chose the 5% and 95% quantiles of the resulting distribution to represent predictive
 228 uncertainty related to model calibration.

229 Parameter conditioning was repeated using data from the year 2003 (Table 3). In
 230 addition, the results from this analysis were used to update the previously obtained
 231 likelihoods in the 2004 calibration, making use of the Bayes theorem:

$$232 \quad L(\Theta_j | Y) = L(Y | \Theta_j)L_0(\Theta_j)/C \quad (10)$$

233 Where $L_0(\Theta_j)$ is a prior likelihood measure for the parameter set Θ_j , $L(Y|\Theta_j)$ is the
 234 likelihood measure obtained when conditioning on the new data set, $L(\Theta_j|Y)$ is the
 235 posterior likelihood after updating, and C is a scaling constant. In this way, if a
 236 parameter set performed badly in one of the calibration periods (i.e. it was non-
 237 behavioural), the combined likelihood yielded a value of zero.

238 **Results**

239 *Radiative transfer and soil surface resistance*

240 The value of the extinction coefficient of net radiation (κ) was *ca.* 0.9, yielding an
241 acceptable simulation of the overall diurnal course of net radiation within the forest.
242 However, this approach could not reproduce the radiation peaks in the observations,
243 which approached 250 W m^{-2} in some occasions (Fig. 1a). Soil heat flux diurnal course
244 was appropriately modelled using multiple regression ($G=0.19*R_{n,s,t-1} + 2.61*T +$
245 $188.51*\theta_{0-15}$; $R^2=0.58;n=480$), but again, the peaky dynamics of G was always not
246 adequately simulated (Fig. 1b).

247 Soil evaporation measurements used for parameterising r_s^s were always below 0.15 mm
248 day^{-1} and the coefficients of the power function relating r_s^s to θ_{0-15} were $b_1=8.74 \text{ s m}^{-1}$
249 and $b_2=-2.55$ ($R^2=0.43, n=14, P=0.011$).

250 *Model performance with the best parameter set from the Monte Carlo procedure*

251 We first ran the model using the best parameter set ($E_f=0.81$; Table 2) obtained after
252 30,000 runs of the model. The relationship between measured and observed values of
253 instantaneous E_c varied across years, with slopes significantly lower than unity (Table
254 4). We examined diurnal simulations under different evaporative demand and soil
255 moisture conditions during selected periods (Fig. 2). In general, the model tended to
256 overestimate E_c . Model residuals tended to increase at higher D_f and T values (data not
257 shown). We did not find any relationship between model residuals and SMD_{30-60}
258 (measured between 30 and 60 cm depth), obtained from weekly TDR measurements
259 (data not shown).

260 Model performance was improved at the daily scale, with slopes close to one except for
261 the year 2004 (Table 4). Daily E_c was generally overestimated by the model, especially
262 during the year 2005 (Fig. 3), with E_f showing a negative value (Table 4). Model
263 residuals calculated on a daily basis did not show any obvious pattern with D_f , T or
264 SMD_{0-30} (data not shown). Maximum soil evaporation rates were estimated at less than

265 0.7 mm day⁻¹, although values between 0.1 and 0.5 mm day⁻¹ were the most frequent
266 (Fig. 3). On a daily basis, the ratio between modelled E_s and measured E_c was below 0.3
267 for almost 80% of the days during the growing season (days 140-300), but this situation
268 changed for non-growing season periods, when only a 40% of the days E_s/E_c fell below
269 0.3.

270 *Parameter space in the G_s model*

271 When the model was conditioned against data from the year 2004, 525 parameter sets
272 were declared behavioural. Scatter plots of model efficiency against each parameter
273 value showed that the range of the parameters $G_{s,ref}$ and m was noticeably constrained by
274 the 2004 calibration data (Fig. 4a). E_f peaked at values of $G_{s,ref}$ about 4.0 mm s⁻¹ and
275 values of m of about 3.0 mm s⁻¹ ln kPa⁻¹. The calculated value of relative sensitivity of
276 G_s to $\ln D$ ($m/G_{s,ref}$) was constrained at values lower than unity. For the rest of
277 parameters, positive values of E_f were found across the whole sampled range (Fig. 4a).
278 Differences in the cumulative distributions between behavioural (525 parameter sets in
279 total) and non-behavioural models were clear for $G_{s,ref}$ and m , and also evident for T_{opt}
280 and f_0 (Fig. 4b). Values of T_{opt} in the central part of the sampled range (15-25 °C) were
281 less probable than values at the extremes, and for f_0 , values were mostly between 0.3
282 and 0.9. Remarkably, the parameters controlling the response to R_n and the threshold for
283 reduction due to SMD₀₋₃₀ ($R_{n,0.5}$ and s , respectively) showed identical, almost uniform
284 distributions for behavioural and non-behavioural sets (Fig. 4b).
285 Substantial differences were found when the model was constrained against 2003 data
286 (Fig. 5). To begin with the number of behavioural models (160 parameter sets), was
287 much lower than in the initial GLUE calibration for the year 2004. The scatter plots
288 showed that positive values of E_f were less frequent at high $G_{s,ref}$ and m ($G_{s,ref} > 6.0$ and
289 $m > 5.0$) (Fig. 5a).

290 Examining the interactions between pairs of parameters in the behavioural sets after
291 calibration with 2004 data, we found that at a given value of $m/G_{s,ref}$ between 0.6-0.8,
292 high efficiencies were distributed across a wide range of s and f_0 (Fig. 6a,b). Noticeably,
293 high efficiencies were also found in the extreme values of T_{opt} (Fig. 6c). If behavioural
294 models conditioned on 2003 data were considered instead, the regions with the best
295 model performance were more clearly delimited (Fig. 6d,e,f). Contrarily to what
296 occurred when conditioning on 2004 data, parameter sets with high E_f values were
297 found with T_{opt} values around the middle of the chosen parameter range (compare Figs.
298 6c and 6f).

299 The two parameters defining the response of G_s to soil moisture deficit were also more
300 sensitive when calibrating against 2003 data. Only the interquartile ranges of $G_{s,ref}$, m ,
301 and to a lesser extent, f_0 , changed appreciably with the data period used for conditioning
302 (Fig. 7). The interquartile ranges of the parameters in the models retained after
303 updating the 2004 calibration with 2003 data, showed how $m/G_{s,ref}$ was constrained
304 around 0.6, and s and f_0 were centered around 0.6 and 0.45, respectively (Fig. 7).

305 *Predictive uncertainty of the evapotranspiration model*

306 The uncertainty bounds calculated on the basis of behavioural models for the 2004
307 calibration period, contained most of the observations during 2003 and 2004, although
308 predictive uncertainty was large for the 2003 dry summer (Fig. 8a).

309 When uncertainty bounds were calculated for the year 2005 (validation), most of the
310 observations fell out of the 5% and 95% uncertainty envelope or were close to the
311 inferior 5% limit (Fig. 8a).

312 Only 44 parameter sets were retained as behavioural when updating likelihoods
313 obtained with 2004 data with those resulting from conditioning on 2003 data .

314 Uncertainty bounds calculated on the basis of these parameter sets (Fig. 8b) were

315 generally narrower than those obtained with behavioural models from parameter
316 conditioning with 2004 data (Fig. 8a). This is particularly appreciable in the reduction
317 of the uncertainty band for the dry summer period of 2003. Nevertheless, from the end
318 of the year 2004, the uncertainty limits still failed to contain the observations.
319 Finally, we examined the meteorological conditions under which the uncertainty limits
320 failed to contain the observations. Although we observed that at high values of daytime-
321 averaged D_r ($D_r > 1.5$ kPa) the uncertainty bounds tended to encompass most of the
322 observations (73% of the observations were within the 5-95% uncertainty limits), we
323 could not find further evidence relating model performance to particular meteorological
324 or soil moisture conditions.

325

326 **4. Discussion**

327 *Forest floor micrometeorology and soil evaporation*

328 Our simple representation of radiative transfer and soil heat flux did not allow for a
329 precise simulation of understorey fluxes. However, the use of the Lambert-Beer law
330 yielded appropriate descriptions of diurnal dynamics of net radiation at the forest floor
331 (Fig. 1). The observed κ for net radiation was larger than the values reported elsewhere
332 for vegetation types (Kustas and Norman, 1999). The multiple regression approach
333 employed to derive G reproduced correctly the influence of soil moisture and the lag
334 between radiative input and soil heat flux (Kustas and Norman, 1999), but the fine
335 resolution simulation of G would require more precise estimations of $R_{n,s}$.

336 Measured soil evaporation during 2005 was very low as a result of the low soil moisture
337 content in the topsoil layers. However, the obtained function of soil surface resistance,
338 similar to other formulations found in the literature (Domingo et al., 1999; Wallace,
339 1995), resulted in typical maximum values of E_s under moist soil conditions, close to

340 those found by Wilson et al. (2000) in a temperate deciduous forest. Similarly, soil
341 evaporation rates in a Douglas-fir stand also increased from 0.2 to 0.4 mm day⁻¹ when
342 soil moisture conditions changed from dry to wet (Schaap and Bouten, 1997).

343 *Performance of the model using best-fit parameters*

344 We used the model with best-fit parameters to illustrate model performance under
345 different environmental conditions. Although we observed patterns in model residuals
346 with respect to D_r and T at the 15-min time step, we did not find them when model
347 residuals were obtained from daily values of modelled and observed E_c . The no
348 consideration of capacitances in the trunk, may have precluded the correct simulation of
349 diurnal courses of E_c when water stored in sapwood is being used to meet evaporative
350 demand (Phillips et al., 1997).

351 The model with the best parameter set from the GLUE analysis using data from the year
352 2004 showed a relatively good performance when assessed against data from year 2003,
353 which included a severe summer drought (Table 4, Fig. 3). However, comparatively,
354 model efficiency yielded negative values for the year 2005. Whether the poor
355 performance of the model was related to the prevailing meteorological or soil moisture
356 conditions during the year 2005, will be discussed further in the next sections. For this
357 purpose we will compare the predictive uncertainty bounds yielded by the model after
358 the GLUE analysis with the daily E_c observations.

359 *Parameter space in the G_s model*

360 Parameter conditioning on 2004 and 2003 data revealed that some information was
361 missing on the behaviour of the system in the 2004 data set. When using 2004 data for
362 calibration, parameters controlling the soil moisture response of G_s were insensitive.
363 Moreover, the T_{opt} parameter was constrained on values in the extreme of the
364 temperature range, in clear disagreement with the usual temperature optimum for

365 *P.sylvestris* (Beadle et al., 1985; Stewart, 1988). When the model was calibrated with
366 2003 data, however, both parameters in $f_3(\text{SMD}_{0-30})$ became sensitive, especially f_0 , and
367 T_{opt} lied preferentially between 15 and 20 °C.

368 The reason why the model was sensitive to soil moisture parameters only when
369 calibrated against 2003 data, could be explained because the summer drought of 2003
370 was longer and more intense than in 2004 (Poyatos et al., 2005). This fact suggests that
371 a lengthy dry period is necessary to detect G_s sensitivity to soil moisture parameters. It
372 may also point at the need for including the influence of the whole soil profile on
373 physiological regulation of G_s , not only the upper 30 cm. Although some studies show
374 that tree response to drought is closely related to moisture availability in the first
375 centimeters of the soil, where fine root density is highest (Warren et al., 2005) it could
376 be otherwise in the seasonally-dry Mediterranean climate we have studied. In this
377 direction, we found that the fraction of G_s remaining after $\text{SMD}_{0-30}=1$ (parameter f_0)
378 showed a lower range when the model was conditioned on 2003 data (Fig. 7). A low f_0
379 means a stronger reduction of G_s when there is no water availability in the upper soil,
380 which might be linked to more depleted water reserves in deeper soil layers during 2003
381 (Rubio, 2005).

382 The average value of $G_{s,\text{ref}}$ for the behavioural models was 12% lower when the model
383 was conditioned on 2003 data, while the reduction in m was higher (35%). This resulted
384 in a decline in $m/G_{s,\text{ref}}$, and therefore, during the dry period, the trees did not show an
385 enhanced sensitivity of G_s to D (Irvine et al., 2004). There is a noticeable similarity
386 between the obtained $m/G_{s,\text{ref}}$ and the theoretical slope between $G_{s,\text{ref}}$ and $\ln D$ ($dG_s/d\ln D$
387 ≈ 0.6) predicted by a hydraulic model assuming stomatal control of water potential to
388 avoid cavitation and corroborated against an extensive survey of leaf and canopy-level
389 observations (Oren et al., 1999). Indeed, Scots pine closes stomata to avoid substantial

390 xylem embolism (Irvine et al., 1998). Recent studies have shown the consistency of the
391 Jarvis-type model of G_s with hydraulic theory (Mackay et al., 2003a), although they still
392 recognise the influence of parameter compensation which characterizes these
393 multiplicative models (Mackay et al., 2003b).

394 *Predictive uncertainty of the evapotranspiration model*

395 Using the GLUE methodology we explored the predictive uncertainty of the
396 evapotranspiration model, and showed that, including additional data from a dry period
397 (year 2003) to update the original calibration with 2004 data, the 5-95 % uncertainty
398 bounds were reduced (Fig. 8). However, we could not find a relationship between
399 particular meteorological and soil moisture conditions and the fact of the uncertainty
400 bounds encompassing the observations or not (i.e. we could not assure whether the
401 model did not perform well more frequently under wet conditions, for example). In
402 addition, the uncertainty bounds failed to encompass most of the daily E_c observations
403 from the end of the year 2004 and during the whole period of 2005 (Fig. 8).

404 Even after an extensive sampling of the parameter space, parameter variation alone
405 could not explain the disagreement between model and observations. Similar difficulties
406 arose with the hydrological model TOPMODEL when it was applied to Mediterranean
407 catchments with long dry periods (Piñol et al., 1997). Therefore, the current model
408 structure could not account for all the physiological processes regulating long-term E_c in
409 the studied stand (Franks and Beven, 1997).

410 *Limitations of the employed model*

411 Stomatal conductance has been shown to be tightly linked to hydraulic conductance of
412 the soil-to-leaf pathway (Irvine et al., 1998; Meinzer and Grantz, 1990) which in turn
413 can be reduced by drought-induced (Tyree and Sperry, 1988) or freeze-thaw embolisms
414 (Sperry and Sullivan, 1992). Both situations must have surely arisen during the study

415 period, which included an acute summer drought (summer 2003), and an extended dry
416 period between autumn 2004 and spring 2005, which included some days of extremely
417 low temperatures (Poyatos, 2006). This drought during a period when soil moisture is
418 usually recovered from summer water deficits (Gallart et al., 2002), is extremely
419 unusual and might have even been responsible for the mortality of Scots pine
420 individuals in locations close to the study area at the end of the spring of the year 2005
421 (personal observation). Considering these severe physiological consequences of drought
422 it is very likely that drastic changes in hydraulic conductance, not included in the
423 stomatal conductance model used in the present study, might have limited the predictive
424 capacity of the model to simulate long-term observations of E_c .

425 Jarvis-type G_s models are attractive because of their simplicity and the relatively good
426 results in predicting transpiration fluxes from forest canopies, and have therefore been
427 widely used in models needing a parameterization of land-surface water vapour
428 exchange (Bartlett et al., 2003). This model or similar approaches (Lohammar et al.,
429 1980) have been successfully applied to other Scots pine stands (Iritz et al., 1999;
430 Lagergren and Lindroth, 2002; Stewart, 1988), but never under the conditions of a
431 seasonally-dry Mediterranean mountain climate.

432 Recent comparisons showed that coupled models and more physically-based approaches
433 with less calibration effort may produce better results than the Jarvis multiplicative
434 model (Falge, 2005; Misson et al., 2004). Some of these models include how plant and
435 soil hydraulic resistances vary with water supply and demand (Williams et al., 2001).
436 Finally, soil water extraction should also be simulated to avoid the use of soil moisture
437 as an input variable to the model.

438 **Conclusions**

439 A two-layer interactive model with a Jarvis-type submodel of canopy conductance
440 yielded acceptable simulations of daily E_c for the calibration periods of 2004 and 2003.
441 Soil evaporation was also reasonably reproduced by the model, but it only represented a
442 small fraction of the total evapotranspiration during the growing season. The GLUE
443 calibration showed that the parameters controlling the stomatal aperture and sensitivity
444 to vapour pressure deficit were the most relevant, and their values were in close
445 agreement with hydraulic regulation of stomatal conductance. The use of data from two
446 distinct calibration periods reduced the predictive uncertainty of the model and showed
447 a high sensitivity of the model to soil moisture parameters when data included a long
448 summer drought period. However, the model calibrated with two years of data failed to
449 adequately simulate the validation period of 2005; the lack of an appropriate description
450 of the variation of plant and soil hydraulic resistances might preclude the precise
451 simulation of long-term E_c with this model in Mediterranean mountain areas.

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462 **References**

- 463 Ball, J.T., Woodrow, I.E. and Berry, J.A., 1987. A model predicting stomatal
464 conductance and its contribution to the control of photosynthesis under different
465 environmental conditions. *Progress in Photosynthesis Research*, 4: 221-224.
- 466 Bartlett, P.A., McCaughey, J.H., Lafleur, P.M. and Verseghy, D.L., 2003. Modelling
467 evapotranspiration at three boreal forest stands using the class: Tests of
468 parameterizations for canopy conductance and soil evaporation. *International
469 Journal of Climatology*, 23(4): 427-451.
- 470 Beadle, C.L., Neilson, R.E., Talbot, H. and Jarvis, P.G., 1985. Stomatal conductance
471 and photosynthesis in a mature Scots Pine forest. II. Dependence on
472 environmental variables of single shoots. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 22(22):
473 573-586.
- 474 Beadle, C.L., Talbot, H. and Jarvis, P.G., 1982. Canopy structure and leaf area index in
475 a mature Scots pine forest. *Forestry*, 55: 105-127.
- 476 Beven, K. and Binley, A., 1992. The future of distributed models: model calibration and
477 uncertainty prediction. *Hydrological Processes*, 6(3): 279-298.
- 478 Beven, K. and Freer, J., 2001. Equifinality, data assimilation, and uncertainty estimation
479 in mechanistic modelling of complex environmental systems using the GLUE
480 methodology. *Journal of Hydrology*, 249(1-4): 11-29.
- 481 Camillo, P.J. and Gurney, R.J., 1986. A resistance parameter for bare soil evaporation
482 models. *Soil Science*, 141: 95-105.
- 483 Choudhury, B.J. and Monteith, J.L., 1988. A four-layer model for the heat budget of
484 homogeneous land surfaces. *Quarterly Journal - Royal Meteorological Society*,
485 114(480): 373-398.

486 Daamen, C.C. and McNaughton, K.G., 2000. Modeling energy fluxes from sparse
487 canopies and understories. *Agronomy Journal*, 92(5): 837-847.

488 Daamen, C.C., Simmonds, L.P., Wallace, J.S., Laryea, K.B. and Sivakumar, M.V.K.,
489 1993. Use of microlysimeters to measure evaporation from sandy soils.
490 *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 65(3-4): 159-173.

491 Domingo, F., Villagarcía, L., Brenner, A.J. and Puigdefábregas, J., 1999.
492 Evapotranspiration model for semi-arid shrub-lands teste against data from SE
493 Spain. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 95: 67-84.

494 Ewers, B.E. and Oren, R., 2000. Analyses of assumptions and errors in the calculation
495 of stomatal conductance from sap flux measurements. *Tree physiology*, 20: 579-
496 589.

497 Falge, E., 2005. Comparison of surface energy exchange models with eddy flux data in
498 forest and grassland ecosystems of Germany. *Ecological modelling*, 188(2-4):
499 174-216.

500 Fisher, J.B., DeBiase, T.A., Qi, Y., Xu, M. and Goldstein, A.H., 2005.
501 Evapotranspiration models compared on a Sierra Nevada forest ecosystem.
502 *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 20(6): 783-896.

503 Franks, S.W. and Beven, K.J., 1997. Bayesian estimation of uncertainty in land surface-
504 atmosphere flux predictions. *Journal of Geophysical Research D: Atmospheres*,
505 102(20): 23991.

506 Franks, S.W., Beven, K.J., Quinn, P.F. and Wright, I.R., 1997. On the sensitivity of
507 soil-vegetation-atmosphere transfer (SVAT) schemes: Equifinality and the
508 problem of robust calibration. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 86(1-2): 63.

509 Gallart, F., Llorens, P., Latron, J. and Regüés, D., 2002. Hydrological processes and
510 their seasonal controls in a small Mediterranean mountain catchment in the
511 Pyrenees. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 6: 527-537.

512 Granier, A., 1985. Une nouvelle méthode pour la mesure du flux de sève brute dans le
513 tronc des arbres. *Annales des Sciences Forestières*, 42: 193-200.

514 Granier, A. and Loustau, D., 1994. Measuring and modelling the transpiration of a
515 maritime pine canopy from sap-flow data. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*,
516 71: 61-81.

517 Hanson, P.J., 2004. Oak forest carbon and water simulations: model intercomparisons
518 and evaluation against independent data. *Ecological monographs*, 74(3): 443-
519 489.

520 Iritz, Z., Lindroth, A., Heikinheimo, M., Grelle, A. and Kellner, E., 1999. Test of a
521 modified Shuttleworth-Wallace estimate of boreal forest evaporation.
522 *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 98-99: 605-619.

523 Irvine, J. et al., 2004. Age-related changes in ecosystem structure and function and
524 effects on water and carbon exchange in ponderosa pine. *Tree Physiology*, 24:
525 753-763.

526 Irvine, J., Perks, M.P., Magnani, F. and Grace, J., 1998. The response of *Pinus sylvestris*
527 to drought: stomatal control of transpiration and hydraulic conductance. *Tree*
528 *Physiology*, 18: 393-402.

529 Jarvis, P.G., 1976. The interpretation of the variations in leaf water potential and
530 stomatal conductance found in canopies in the field. *Philosophical Transactions*
531 *of the Royal Society of London B Biological Sciences*, 273: 593-610.

532 Kustas, W.P. and Norman, J.M., 1999. Evaluation of soil and vegetation heat flux
533 predictions using a simple two-source model with radiometric temperatures for
534 partial canopy cover. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 94: 13-29.

535 Lagergren, F. and Lindroth, A., 2002. Transpiration response to soil moisture in pine
536 and spruce trees in Sweden. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 112(2): 67-85.

537 Lohammar, T., Larsson, S., Linder, S. and Falk, S., 1980. FAST - simulation model of
538 gaseous exchange in Scots pine. In: T. Persson (Editor), *Structure and Function*
539 *of Northern Coniferous Forests - An Ecosystem Study*. *Ecological Bulletins*, pp.
540 505-523.

541 Llorens, P. and Gallart, F., 2000. A simplified method for forest water storage capacity
542 measurement. *Journal of Hydrology*, 240(1-2): 131.

543 Mackay, D.S. et al., 2003a. Physiological tradeoffs in the parameterization of a model
544 of canopy transpiration. *Advances in Water Resources*, 26(2): 179-194.

545 Mackay, D.S., Samanta, S., Nemani, R.R. and Band, L.E., 2003b. Multi-objective
546 parameter estimation for simulating canopy transpiration in forested watersheds.
547 *Journal of Hydrology*, 277(3-4): 230-247.

548 Massman, W.J., 1992. Correcting errors associated with soil heat flux measurements
549 and estimating soil thermal properties from soil temperature and heat flux plate
550 data. *Agricultural & Forest Meteorology*, 59(3-4): 249.

551 Meinzer, F.C. and Grantz, D.A., 1990. Stomatal and hydraulic conductance in growing
552 sugarcane -stomatal adjustment to water transport capacity. *Plant Cell and*
553 *Environment*, 13: 383-388.

554 Misson, L., Panek, J.A. and Goldstein, A.H., 2004. A comparison of three approaches to
555 modeling leaf gas exchange in annually drought-stressed ponderosa pine forests.
556 *Tree Physiology*, 24(5): 529.

557 Mo, X. and Beven, K., 2004. Multi-objective parameter conditioning of a three-source
558 wheat canopy model. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 122(1-2): 39-63.

559 Nash, J.E. and Sutcliffe, J.V., 1970. River flow forecasting through conceptual models:
560 Part I - A discussion of principles. *Journal of Hydrology*, 10(3): 282.

561 Oren, R. et al., 1999. Survey and synthesis of intra- and interspecific variation in
562 stomatal sensitivity to vapour pressure deficit. *Plant Cell and Environment*,
563 22(12): 1515-1526.

564 Phillips, N., Nagchaudhuri, A., R.Oren and G.Katul, 1997. Time constant for water
565 transport in Loblolly pine trees estimated from time series of evaporative
566 demand and stem sapflow. *Trees*, 11: 412-419.

567 Piñol, J., Beven, K. and Freer, J., 1997. Modelling the hydrological response of
568 mediterranean catchments, Prades, Catalonia. The use of distributed models as
569 aids to hypothesis formulation. *Hydrological Processes*, 11(9): 1287-1306.

570 Poyatos, R., 2006. Measuring and modelling transpiration of pine and oak forest stands
571 in a Mediterranean mountain area (Vallcebre, NE Spain). PhD Thesis,
572 Universitat de Barcelona, Barcelona, 165 pp.

573 Poyatos, R., Čermák, J. and Llorens, P., 2007. Variation in the radial patterns of sap
574 flux density in pubescent oak (*Quercus pubescens* Willd.) and its implications
575 for tree and stand transpiration measurements. *Tree Physiology*, 27: 537-548.

576 Poyatos, R., Latron, J. and Llorens, P., 2003. Land-use and land cover change after
577 agricultural abandonment. The case of a Mediterranean Mountain Area (Catalan
578 Pyrenees). *Mountain Research and Development*, 23(4): 52-58.

579 Poyatos, R., Llorens, P. and Gallart, F., 2005. Transpiration of montane *Pinus sylvestris*
580 L. and *Quercus pubescens* Willd. forest stands measured with sap flow sensors
581 in NE Spain. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 9: 493-505.

582 Rubio, C., 2005. Hidrodinámica de los suelos de un área de montaña media
583 mediterránea sometida a cambios de uso y cubierta, Universitat Autònoma de
584 Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain, 194 pp.

585 Schaap, M.G. and Bouten, W., 1997. Forest floor evaporation in a dense Douglas fir
586 stand. *Journal of Hydrology*, 193(1-4): 97-113.

587 Shuttleworth, W.J. and Gurney, R.J., 1990. The theoretical relationship between foliage
588 temperature and canopy resistance in sparse crops. *Quarterly Journal of the*
589 *Royal Meteorological Society*, 116: 497-519.

590 Shuttleworth, W.J. and Wallace, J.S., 1985. Evaporation from sparse crops- an energy
591 combination theory. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 111:
592 839-855.

593 Sperry, J.S. and Sullivan, J.E.M., 1992. Xylem embolism in response to freeze-thaw
594 cycles and water stress in ring-porous, diffuse-porous, and conifer species. *Plant*
595 *Physiology*, 100: 605-613.

596 Stewart, J.B., 1988. Modelling surface conductance of pine forest. *Agricultural and*
597 *Forest Meteorology*, 43: 19-35.

598 Sturm, N., Köstner, B., Hartung, W. and Tenhunen, J.D., 1998. Environmental and
599 endogenous controls on leaf- and stand-level water conductance in a Scots pine
600 plantation. *Annales des Sciences Forestières*, 55: 237-253.

601 Tyree, M.T. and Sperry, J.S., 1988. Do woody plants operate near the point of
602 catastrophic xylem dysfunction by dynamic water stress? *Plant Physiology*, 88:
603 574-580.

604 Wallace, J.S., 1995. Calculating evaporation: resistance to factors. *Agricultural and*
605 *Forest Meteorology*, 73(3-4): 353-366.

606 Warren, J.M., Meinzer, F.C., Brooks, J.R. and Domec, J.C., 2005. Vertical stratification
607 of soil water storage and release dynamics in Pacific Northwest coniferous
608 forests. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 130: 39-58.

609 Whitehead, D. and Jarvis, P.G., 1981. Coniferous forests and plantations. In: T.T.
610 Kozlowski (Editor), *Water Deficits and Plant Growth*. Academic Press, New
611 York, pp. 49-152.

612 Wilson, K.B., Hanson, P.J. and Baldocchi, D.D., 2000. Factors controlling evaporation
613 and energy partitioning beneath a deciduous forest over an annual cycle.
614 *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 102(2-3): 83-103.

615 Williams, M., Bond, B.J. and Ryan, M.G., 2001. Evaluating different soil and plant
616 hydraulic constraints on tree function using a model and sap flow data from
617 ponderosa pine. *Plant Cell and Environment*, 24(7): 679-690.

618

619

620

621 Table 1. List of symbols and units used in this paper.

Description	Symbol	Units
<i>Canopy structure and aerodynamics</i>		
Canopy height	h	m
Leaf Area Index	LAI	$\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-2}$
Roughness length	z_0	m
<i>Radiation transfer and soil heat flux</i>		
Above-canopy net radiation	R_n	W m^{-2}
Canopy net radiation	$R_{n,c}$	W m^{-2}
Below-canopy net radiation	$R_{n,s}$	W m^{-2}
Extinction coefficient for R_n	κ	
<i>Resistance network</i>		
Plant surface resistance	r_s^c	s m^{-1}
Soil aerodynamic resistance	r_a^s	s m^{-1}
Soil surface resistance	r_s^s	s m^{-1}
<i>Parameters of the G_s model</i>		
Fraction of G_s when $\text{SMD}_{0-30}=1$	f_0	adimensional
Canopy stomatal conductance	G_s	mm s^{-1}
Reference conductance at 1 kPa	$G_{s,\text{ref}}$	mm s^{-1}
Absolute sensitivity of G_s to $\ln D$	m	$\text{mm s}^{-1} \ln \text{kPa}^{-1}$
R_n at half-saturation of G_s	$R_{n,0.5}$	W m^{-2}
Threshold of G_s reduction with SMD_{0-30}	s	
Maximum time for G_s	t_{max}	hours
Minimum time for G_s	t_{min}	hours
Time optimum for G_s	t_{opt}	hours
Maximum air temperature for G_s	T_{max}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Minimum air temperature for G_s	T_{min}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Optimum air temperature for G_s	T_{opt}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
<i>Soil parameters</i>		
Soil moisture (0-30 cm)	θ_{0-30}	$\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$
Soil moisture deficit (0-30 cm)	SMD_{0-30}	adimensional
Soil moisture deficit (30-60 cm)	SMD_{30-60}	adimensional
Soil moisture 0-15 cm	θ_{0-15}	$\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$
Soil moisture (0-15 cm) at field capacity	$\theta_{0-15,\text{FC}}$	$\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$
Parameter of soil surface resistance equation	b_1	s m^{-1}
Parameter of soil surface resistance equation	b_2	adimensional
Saturated vapour pressure at soil temperature	$e_{T_s}^*$	kPa
<i>Other</i>		
Vapour pressure deficit at reference height	D_r	kPa
Canopy transpiration	E_c	$\text{mm s}^{-1}, \text{mm day}^{-1}$
Model efficiency	E_f	adimensional
Vapour pressure at reference height	e_r	kPa
Soil evaporation	E_s	$\text{mm s}^{-1}, \text{mm day}^{-1}$
Air temperature at reference height	T_a	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Wind speed at reference height	u	m s^{-1}

622

623 Table 2. Range of the uniform distribution from which the parameters included in the
 624 GLUE analysis were sampled. The values of the best parameter set from the Monte
 625 Carlo procedure using data from the year 2004 are also shown.

Parameter	Minimum	Maximum	Best parameter set	Units
$G_{s,ref}$	2.0	10.0	4.56	mm s ⁻¹
m	1.0	10.0	2.84	mm s ⁻¹ ln kPa ⁻¹
$R_{n,0.5}$	0	500	239.39	W m ⁻²
s	0.2	1	0.21	Adimensional
f_0	0	1	0.575	Adimensional
t_{opt}	4	20	13.03	hour
T_{opt}	5	35	7.98	°C
z_o	1	6	3.19	m

626

627 Table 3. Characteristics of the datasets used in the calibration and validation stages.
 628 One-year periods are shown for better comparison of meteorological conditions across
 629 years. Maximum values of vapour pressure deficit (D_r) are shown in brackets.

Year	Period (days)	Average D_r (kPa)	Rainfall (mm)	θ_{0-30} ($\text{cm}^3\text{cm}^{-3}$)	Calibration procedures	
					Boundary- line	GLUE
<i>Datasets</i>						
2003	205-365	0.68	433	0.24	Validation	Calibration ^{*†}
2004	1-362	0.56	644	0.23	Calibration *	Calibration *
2005	1-212	0.77	312	0.19	Validation	Validation
<i>Equal-length periods</i>						
2003-	July 2003-	0.53			-	-
2004	June 2004	(3.17)	824	0.24		
2004-	July 2004-	0.77			-	-
2005	June 2005	(2.78)	566	0.19		

630 ^{*} The model has been validated separately for each year and therefore calibration data
 631 has also been used for validation.

632 [†] Dataset used to update likelihoods obtained when the model was constrained with
 633 2004 data.
 634

635

636

637 Table 4. Performance of the model in terms of E_c using best parameter set from the
 638 Monte Carlo simulations. Number of observations (N), slope, intercept and
 639 coefficient of determination (R^2) of the linear regression between observed and
 640 simulated values, and model efficiency (E_f) for different periods at the instantaneous
 641 and daily time scales.

	N	Slope	Intercept	R^2	E_f
<i>15-min</i>					
2003	5010	0.77	1.30E-05	0.69	0.49
2004	11091	0.64	1.13E-05	0.65	0.65
2005	5968	0.71	2.00E-05	0.52	-0.18
<i>Daily</i>					
2003	151	0.98	0.250	0.85	0.43
2004	323	0.72	0.140	0.85	0.81
2005	160	0.96	0.500	0.75	-0.18

643

644

1 FIGURE CAPTIONS

2 Fig. 1. Modelled and measured (a) Net radiation below the canopy ($R_{n,s}$) and (b) soil
3 heat flux (G).

4
5 Fig 2. Observed and modelled E_c rates during two periods with varying soil moisture
6 deficit and vapour pressure deficit conditions.

7
8 Fig 3. Time series of modelled and observed canopy transpiration (E_c) and modelled
9 soil evaporation (E_s) at the daily scale for the whole study period.

10
11 Fig 4. Parameter conditioning of the evapotranspiration model with sap flow data from
12 year 2004 after 30,000 Monte Carlo realisations. (a) Plot of daily efficiency against
13 parameter values included in the GLUE analysis (Table 2). Only simulations with $E_f > 0$
14 are shown. (b) Cumulative likelihood distribution of the parameters, for behavioural
15 ($E_f > 0.75$) and non-behavioural parameter sets ($E_f < 0.75$).

16
17 Fig 5. Parameter conditioning of the evapotranspiration model with sap flow data from
18 year 2003 after 30,000 Monte Carlo realisations. (a) Plot of daily efficiency against
19 parameter values included in the GLUE analysis (Table 2). Only simulations with $E_f > 0$
20 are shown. (b) Cumulative likelihood distribution of the parameters, for behavioural
21 ($E_f > 0.75$) and non-behavioural models ($E_f < 0.75$).

22
23 Fig. 6. Values of model efficiency of behavioural parameter sets conditioned on 2004
24 data (left column) and 2003 data (right column) related to the values of pairs of
25 parameters in the G_s model.

1 Fig. 7. Average value (dots) and interquartile range (bars) of selected parameters for
2 behavioural models when the model was constrained with (a) 2004 data, (b) 2003 data
3 and (c) the obtained likelihoods from both GLUE analysis were combined as described
4 in the text.

5

6 Fig. 8. Uncertainty bounds (5% and 95%) of daily transpiration (E_c) (shaded area) in
7 relation with observed E_c (black line). a) For behavioural models when conditioned on
8 2004 data and b) for behavioural models after updating the likelihoods obtained in the
9 calibration with data from the year 2004 with the data from the year 2003.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

